

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE CORRESPONDENCE DEPARTMENT

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ABSTRACT

the article describes the methodological aspects of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities of Uzbekistan, especially in the correspondence department. The question is raised that the functional principle of teaching becomes the main thing in teaching the Russian language, and the communicative competence of students is also placed in the center of attention. It talks about an intensive search for new approaches, forms and innovative methods of teaching the Russian language, where the directive model of teaching is replaced by an interactive model, which is more productive and focused on the student's personality.

Learning a foreign language is always associated with the initial complexity of its perception. In non-linguistic universities of Uzbekistan, educational processes are constantly being improved. Teachers of language departments focus on in-depth study of the vocabulary of the target language, and also use innovative techniques that make it possible to clearly convey all the features of mastering Russian speech. Innovative technologies have begun to be introduced in universities thanks to high-quality technical support and the constant search for new teaching methods. They are aimed at using various forms of collaboration between teacher and students [1]. Currently, technologies that increase the impact on each individual student and increase the efficiency of developing competencies are recognized as innovative. The main goal of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities, especially in the correspondence department, is not so much teaching the language system of linguistic competence, but rather mastering communicative competence, i.e. the ability of a person to carry out verbal communication in a particular field of activity using the means of the language being studied.

The basis of communicative competence is a complex of linguistic knowledge and speech skills and abilities that are formed and acquired during classes [4]. The main emphasis in teaching Russian is grammar; phonetics, the lexical composition of the language and oral practice are also important for students. Teachers teach how to communicate correctly in Russian not only in the context of their specialization, but also how to express themselves fluently in everyday life [2].

Currently, we see that global changes have affected:

- goals of studying Russian speech;
- conditions of education;
- needs of students.

An individual approach to each student is relevant, who now themselves determine the linguistic and cultural component of their learning. As a result of training, a specialist can communicate freely in any field, competently using specific professional terminology.

In Russian language lessons in the correspondence department at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, much attention is paid to the speech component; not only dialogues and monologues are heard, but also certain situations are played out. Attention is focused on ensuring that students make independent efforts, study additional material, constantly practice with each other, and do not miss the opportunity to communicate with native speakers.

Knowledge of vocabulary and constant training in conversational speech make it possible to correctly formulate thoughts in Russian. Lexical skills include:

- creating sentences or phrases that have not been used before;
- use of lexical units in different forms and phrases;
- selection of words related to a specific situation, as well as synonyms and antonyms for them;
- recalling and reproducing the necessary lexical elements;
- ability to paraphrase frequently heard sentences;
- at the lexical level, the ability to recall concepts belonging to different categories.

Innovative methods for studying vocabulary help to reveal a number of important points [3]:

- norms of compatibility of some words with others;
- phonetic, spelling and grammatical features of words;
- search for interchangeable constructions for already known words and speech patterns.

The meaning of a word is an important point; its disclosure is achieved by establishing a connection between educational material, in the form of pictures, layouts, objects and other visual material. [2] Visual aids greatly facilitate the perception of a foreign language, increase the amount of material learned and contribute to the effectiveness of the lessons.

The principle of clarity is used for correspondence students with different backgrounds, but it is not the only thing that helps in learning Russian speech. Each teacher combines different methods, means and techniques, taking into account the characteristics of a particular group and pedagogical situation. The teacher selects educational materials and methods of their transmission for the best perception of the language.

Teachers can use many innovative technologies, among which the following deserve special attention:

- technologies of critical thinking;
- gaming technologies;
- case study technology;
- distance learning;
- project method [4].

The use of pedagogical methods must be subject to several principles:

- mastering the language by studying the culture of the people;
- combining subject-language and professionally oriented approaches;
- the use of a variety of tasks, video and audio materials, tests, with the help of which diagnostics and monitoring of language acquisition are carried out.

These principles are feasible only by building the correct model of teaching the Russian language.

Students must try to fully complete all academic assignments, as well as independently study theoretical materials on each topic covered. When working independently, self-testing is done by answering questions and passing tests.

This enables students to successfully master the necessary knowledge for free communication in Russian:

- master professional terminology;
- successfully construct literate sentences from linguistic units and easily express your thoughts in a foreign language;
- evaluate and perceive the speech of other interlocutors.

Thus, well-chosen innovative teaching methods unite all participants in communication, regardless of the initial level of foreign language proficiency.

Priority is given to the student's independent work, which involves, first of all, careful study of additional theoretical materials and educational Internet resources for each topic, self-testing using questions and tests given at the end of the topic, as well as mandatory completion of practical assignments. As for the remaining 50%, depending on the students, it should be noted that no matter what new innovative method the teacher chooses for the student in order to increase his practical mastery of the language, much depends on him, on his diligence, efforts and intelligence. Because the most meaningful and inspiring lesson cannot last more than an hour and a half. At the end of the lesson, outside the doors of the classroom and the university, the student is left alone with his efforts and imagination.

Based on the above, students can be advised to follow the famous saying "Repetition is the mother of learning." The more they repeat the material they have covered, going deeper into it, the better they will be able to remember it. This is due to the emergence of the labor market, competition in Uzbekistan for specialists from domestic and foreign professional schools in order to bring the level of graduates of domestic educational institutions to the level of professional competence of a foreign specialist. Modern methods of teaching the Russian language in universities of Uzbekistan recognize that the difficulties of mastering words, on the one hand, are associated with the peculiarities of the lexical system of the Russian language itself, and on the other, with the specifics of the vocabulary of the students' native language. Since words in the Russian language do not exist in isolation, but in connection with others, students learn vocabulary in interconnection, in comparison, which facilitates the process of mastering the material. In the learning process, a large place should be given to the semantics of words, since it is associated with the correct understanding of the word and its use in speech. The living word of the teacher, his direct appeal to students, the possibility of constant feedback - all this has undoubted advantages. We should always remember: no matter what technical means we use, the central figure in the educational process remains the teacher, and he needs to carefully monitor his speech, have good, clear

pronunciation, and avoid grammatical and stylistic errors.

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